

GEOMETRIYADA EKSTREMAL MASALALAR

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ANNOTATSIYA.

Ekstremumdan foydalanib amaliyotda juda ko’p geometrik masalalar yechiladi, ularni bazilari ushbu maqolada ko’rsatilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: Ekstirimum, geometriya, silindr, balandlik.

Masala. Yuzi $S=75\pi m^2$ bo’lgan tunukadan asosining radiusi R va balandligi H bo’lgan usti ochiq shunday silindr bak yasangki, uning hajmi eng kata bo’lsin.

Yechish. Bakning sig’imi (hajmi) $V=\pi R^2 H$, uni yasash uchun $S = \pi R^2 + 2\pi R H = \pi R^2 + 2\pi R H$ yuzaga ega bo’lgan material ketadi. Bundan H balandlikni topamiz:

$$H = \frac{S - \pi R^2}{2\pi R}$$

U holda bakning sig’imi:

$$V = \pi R^2 \frac{S - \pi R^2}{2\pi R} = \frac{SR - \pi R^3}{2} = V(R)$$

ga teng va u R ga bog’liq funksiyadan iboratdir.

R ning shunday qiymatini topamizki, unda sig’im $V(R)$ maksimum bo’lsin. $V(R)$ dan R ga nisbatan birinchi tartibli hosilani topamiz:

$$V' = \frac{1}{2}(S - 3\pi R^2), \quad V' = 0$$

$$S - 3\pi R^2 = 0 \quad R = \sqrt{\frac{S}{3\pi}} = \sqrt{\frac{75\pi}{3\pi}} = 5m$$

Ikkinchi tartibli hosila $V'' = -3\pi R < 0$ bo’lgani uchun topilgan $R=5$ qiymatda bakning sig’imi eng kata (maksimal) bo’ladi.

Yuqoridagi (A) formuladan bakning balandligini topamiz:

$$\frac{S - \pi R^2}{2\pi R} = \frac{S - \pi \frac{S}{3\pi}}{2\pi \sqrt{\frac{S}{3\pi}}} = \sqrt{\frac{S}{3\pi}} = \sqrt{\frac{75\pi}{3\pi}} = 5m$$

H=

$$\frac{S - \pi R^2}{2\pi R} = \frac{S - \pi \frac{S}{3\pi}}{2\pi \sqrt{\frac{S}{3\pi}}} = \sqrt{\frac{S}{3\pi}} = \sqrt{\frac{75\pi}{3\pi}} = 5m$$

Masala. Sug'orish kanalining ko'ndalang kesimi teng yonli trapetsiya shaklida bo'lib, uning yon tomoni .Bu trapetsiyaning yon tomoni qiyalik burchagi α qanday bo'lganda kanalning ko'ndalang kesim yuzi eng katta bo'ladi?

Yechish. Trapetsiyaning yon tomoni va kichik asosini a deb, kanalning ko'ndalang kesim yuzini α burchakning funksiyasi kabi aniqlaymiz. U xolda yuqoridagi chizmadan:

$$|AB|=a \quad |BE|=a \cos \alpha \quad |DC|=a+2a \cos \alpha \quad CE=a \sin \alpha$$

$$S = \frac{|AB|+|DC|}{2} \cdot |CE| = \frac{2a+2a \cos \alpha}{2} \cdot a \sin \alpha = a^2 (\sin \alpha + \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\alpha)$$

$$\frac{|AB|+|DC|}{2} \cdot |CE| = \frac{2a+2a \cos \alpha}{2} \cdot a \sin \alpha = a^2 (\sin \alpha + \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\alpha)$$

ni hosil qilamiz. Bu α o'zgaruvchining funksiyasidan iborat bo'lgani uchun, uning ekstremumini tekshiramiz:

$$S' = a^2 (\cos \alpha + \cos 2\alpha)$$

Kritik nuqtalarda $S' = 0$, ya'ni $\cos \alpha + \cos 2\alpha = 0$ yoki

$$\cos \frac{3\alpha}{2} \cdot \cos \frac{\alpha}{2} = 0$$

Aniqlanish sohasi $0 < \alpha < \frac{\pi}{2}$ bo'lgani uchun $\cos \frac{\alpha}{2} \neq 0$.

Shuning uchun $\cos \frac{3\alpha}{2} = 0$, bundan $\frac{3\alpha}{2} = \frac{\pi}{2}$ yoki $\alpha = \frac{\pi}{3}$

Endi $\alpha = \frac{\pi}{3}$ bo'lganda S funksiya $[0; \frac{\pi}{2}]$ kesmada eng kata qiymatga erishishini isbot qilamiz.

Xaqiqatdan, $S'' = a^2 (-\sin \alpha - 2 \sin 2\alpha)$,

$$S'' \left(\frac{\pi}{3} \right) = a^2 \left(-\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} - \sqrt{3} \right) = -a^2 \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} < 0$$

Shuning uchun $\alpha = \frac{\pi}{3}$ da funksiya $S'' \left(\frac{\pi}{3} \right) = S''_{max} \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} a^2$

lokal maksimumga ega, $S(0)=0$, $S\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = a^2 < S_{max}\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = a^2 < S_{max}$ bo'lab uchun $\left[0; \frac{\pi}{2}\right]$ kesmada S funksiya eng katta qiymatga erishadi.

MASALA. RADIUSI R BO'LGAN DOIRA ICHIGA CHIZILGAN TO'G'RI TO'RTBURCHAKLARDAN YUZI ENG KATTASINI TOPING?

Yechish. To'g'ri to'rtburchak tomonlaridan birini xx deb belgilasak ikkinchi tomoni o'z-o'zidan

$y = \sqrt{4R^2 - x^2}$ bo'ladi. To'rtburchak yuzi esa $S = x\sqrt{4R^2 - x^2}$

$S = x\sqrt{4R^2 - x^2}$ bo'ladi, bundan xx va $\sqrt{4R^2 - x^2}$ ko'paytuvchilar musbat demak, $S > 0$, $S > 0$, S va S^2 funksiyalar o'zining eng katta qiymatlarini bitta xx nuqtada qabul qiladi. Bu nuqtani topamiz.

$$(S^2)' = (x\sqrt{4R^2 - x^2})^2' = (4R^2 - x^2)' = 8R^2x - 4x^3 = 0$$

$$(S^2)' = (x\sqrt{4R^2 - x^2})^2' = (4R^2 - x^2)' = 8R^2x - 4x^3 = 0$$

$$4x(2R^2 - x^2) = 0 \quad 4x(\sqrt{2R} - x)(\sqrt{2R} + x) = 0 \quad 4x(\sqrt{2R} - x)(\sqrt{2R} + x) = 0$$

$$x_1 = 0 \quad x_2 = \sqrt{2R} \quad x_3 = -\sqrt{2R} \quad x_1 = 0 \quad x_2 = \sqrt{2R} \quad x_3 = -\sqrt{2R}$$

$$x_{max} = \sqrt{2R} \quad x_{max} = -\sqrt{2R} \quad x_{max} = \sqrt{2R} \quad x_{min} = -\sqrt{2R} \quad x_{min} = 0 \quad x_{min} = 0$$

Demak yuzani maksimum nuqtadagi qiymatini hisoblasak,

$$S = (\sqrt{2R}) = 2RS = (\sqrt{2R}) = 2R \quad SS \quad va \quad S^2S^2 \quad funksiyalar \quad eng \quad katta \quad qiymatni \quad x = \sqrt{2R}$$

$x = \sqrt{2R}$ bul qiladi. Bunda to'rtburchakning ikkinchi tomoni ham $y = \sqrt{2R}$ bo'ladi.

Demak to'rtburchakning ikkala tomoni teng ya'ni $y = xy = x$ ekan. Xulosa qilib aytish mumkinki, bu to'rtburchak kvadrat ekan va doiraga ichki chizilgan to'g'ri to'rtburchaklardan yuzi eng kattasi kvadrat bo'lar ekan.

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